

Electronic Terrorism And Its Impact On National Security

Omar Saad Khalid, Warqaa Muhammad Rahim

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Abstract

Due to the technological and technical development that the world has witnessed, and the dependence of most countries on digital technology and cyberspace and their employment in all fields and institutions, these institutions and areas have become vulnerable to penetration by some, whether they are individuals, groups or countries, and this threat that is called electronic terrorism, has become a kind of Types of threats to the security of countries, so in order for the state to maintain its security, whether it is political, social or economic, it must take decisive and quick measures to preserve its security from those threats that did not exclude anyone, whether major countries or third world countries.

Introduction

The importance of the research comes from the extent of the correct understanding of the meaning of national security, and the identification of its dimensions. National security is the ability with which the state is able to preserve its entity from internal and external dangers, and the most prominent of those dangers at the present time is the threat of electronic terrorism. Technology is used in all areas of life threatening the security and stability of countries, especially developed ones, as some people who have knowledge and experience in the technical field can penetrate sensitive files, institutions and centers in the country, and then electronic terrorism has become one of the most serious threats to the national security of countries.

Research Hypothesis

Our main hypothesis in our research is based on: (Despite the advantages and advantages that accompanied the technological development and the digital revolution, it carries with it many risks that threaten society and the state. Countries that adopt advanced technology in their institutions.

The first topic: What is security, its dimensions and levels

Before addressing the concept of national security, we must first get acquainted with the concept of security and what its dimensions are, and then learn about its levels.

First, the concept of security

Before entering into the linguistic and procedural definitions of the concept of security, we must know that security is one of the basic needs of man, which he cannot live without. Since the first day of his life, man has found himself in need of security and safety, because his life was and still is full of various challenges that threaten his being and existence. Security is not one of the concepts that is easy to define. Researchers in security studies have unanimously agreed that it is a vague and complex concept, given its knowledge content that is heavy with values, semantics and feelings. From referring to security in its abstract sense, security in language is the opposite of fear. And the word security is the language of the source of the triple verb safe, secure and safe: that is, reassurance of the soul, calmness of the heart, and the demise of fear. Ibn Manzur said: "I believed, I am safe, and I secured others, that is, against fear, trust against betrayal, faith against infidelity, and faith in the sense of belief. And the opposite of it is denial, so it is said that some people believed in it and some people lied in it." The concept was mentioned in the Holy Qur'an by the Almighty's saying: "So let them worship the Lord of this House who has fed them from hunger and secured them from fear" as well as the Almighty's saying: "Enter it in peace and security"

Hence, most of the literature that defined the concept of security that the concept generally refers to achieving a state of lack of feeling fear, and substituting a feeling of safety in its psychological and physical dimensions for a feeling of fear, and a feeling of safety as a universal desirable human value that is not limited to a particular social group or related to the level of income. The poor, like the rich, need a sense of security and seek to achieve it, even if the enjoyment levels vary. Due to the difficulty of achieving complete security, security has come to be seen as a relative issue subject to seeking to enhance the best conditions for its availability. From the foregoing, most of the definitions appear, including a common denominator for the definition of security, which

is the lack of fear and a sense of safety in every place and time, regardless of differences in gender, age, sect, religion or social classes, as they are among the necessary needs that a person seeks.

Second: Dimensions and levels of security

The components of national security differ from one state to another, because each state has its own circumstances, characteristics and nature. However, there are common denominators among states with regard to national security in its general form, so that the broad outlines of national security are almost identical, and these components and dimensions are a source of strength or weakness for national security. Each of them affects the other, and if some or all of them are threatened, the entire national security will be threatened, and its weakness will prepare ways to penetrate it. These dimensions will be addressed as follows:

The human dimension of security

Security is an innate human need, for a normal person seeks security in all his actions, whether those actions have effects on the soul and the body. material and moral, and participate in demonstrations, political actions, and social demands, and may also fight for security and in search of it security in its human dimension is, in short, liberation from the feeling of insecurity as an alternative to the possibility of a security threat. This dimension can only be achieved under rational, comprehensive and sustainable development policies. Therefore, human security was the goal of all religions, beliefs and philosophies

The political dimension

it means preserving the political entity of a state through developing its capabilities and increasing its national strength. The political dimension of the state's national security is linked to the extent to which democracy is achieved in it. Democratic systems allow the establishment of effective political institutions and lead to an expansion of the volume of political participation and equality among citizens, and this is what It leads to enhancing security and filling gaps that could threaten it. This dimension has two areas:

- A. The internal policy for managing society and overcoming its problems. What is required is the stability of the state within the framework of constitutional legitimacy and directing competition for internal forces, and political trends for the benefit of the nation. on its stated and undeclared goals.
- B. Foreign policy. What is required is to succeed in securing the requirements of national sovereignty and the needs of the state without submitting to any external pressures. This is done through the ability and efficiency of the diplomatic apparatus and how the state uses its sources of power, mobilizes public opinion, and uses the political forces of other countries with vital interests in the region in order to explain the goals of the state. And extend its influence in the international community.

The economic dimension

it means achieving sufficiency and prosperity and protecting economic projects, and it includes the state's ability to control the effects arising from globalization with all it means of liberalizing international trade, ease of transfer of capital, fluctuations in the prices of raw materials, and the possibility of sudden changes in the global economic system as a result of the hegemony of powers. An economy that operates outside the framework of state control and reconciling considerations of economic liberalization, including the control of market forces in the global economy, with the consideration of protecting national security, so that the freedom of market forces does not lead to economic collapse, and economic security also includes securing the basic sources of national income through a diversity of alternatives. .

It can be said that security in its simplest interpretations means providing the appropriate climate for achieving economic growth that would maintain stability for the country and not be exposed to economic problems that threaten its security. The great American pressures were not of a political or military nature in the first place, but rather were of an economic nature

The military dimension

It is the dimension that focuses on the military aspect of the state, especially the armed forces, and their role in protecting the state against any foreign armed threat that threatens its entity or its borders, and it has an external role that is to show its power to the outside world, and it is convinced that this state has the strength to protect it. Its vital interests externally and its realization in the event of resorting to armed force

The environmental dimension

The environmental sector is the most important sector for security in its broad sense, as the ecosystem affects security relations. The growing phenomenon of scarcity leads to the creation of conflicts between countries, especially water scarcity, and many environmental problems, such as water and air pollution, are classified among the issues. Which leads to a high death rate, starvation and deterioration of the general health situation and the interaction of these complex problems with rapid demographic growth exacerbates the risk and then threatens the survival of the individual, his life and his well-being, which clearly highlights the relationship of the ecosystem (environment with the concept of human security) and then the environment has become her. It has an impact on security, so it has become one of its dimensions to enter into the peace and security equation to form a triple (peace, security and environment)

The social dimension

which means social cohesion within a single state with the presence of special differences, whether in religion, race, language ... and within the state there may be sects and ethnicities that have a relationship with other external parties, so these minorities work on adopting methods that conflict with the internal policy of the political system

It is clear from the foregoing that security has different dimensions according to different researchers who dealt with the concept from its research point of view.

Third: levels of security

Security has several levels: the national level, the regional level, the international level, and the individual level. What concerns us in this research is the study of security at the national level or the so-called national security. Before getting to know the concept of national security, it must be noted that, this concept has appeared in the modern era as a result of its increasing importance, as it came to include various aspects of economic, social, political and other life, and the first responsibility of the state became summed up in achieving national security in all its dimensions. Subordinate to the US Senate on defense policy and military structure for the period after World War II, when the Secretary of Defense (James Forstall) referred to the idea of national security as one of the components of the policies of the United States, and the first official body associated with the name of national security established by the United States of America in 1947 is (American National Security Council), as it is entrusted with all matters and issues that affect the entity of the American nation and threaten its security, and since that date this concept began to appear as a term in circulation in Departments of political and strategic studies at the international level.

(Amos Gordon and William Taylor) define national security in its narrow sense as “the physical protection of the people and the territory of the state from external threats,” but in its broad sense it refers to more than the physical protection of the state because it includes the protection of the economic, political, and moral interests of the state and its values that threaten its survival and borders”, As for Muhammad Taha Al-Badawi, he defines national security as “the sum total of the vital interests of the state, such as the protection of the region and independence, and it is ready for the option of war in order to protect and defend the state and sometimes take it above the option of international peace and security.” which determine the rules of movement in regional dealings related to the guarantee and protection of the autonomous entity”(), and despite the different definitions above, they share an essential point that the state must be preserved from any threats that threaten it, whether those dangers are internal or external.

National security is based on two variables

1. The extent to which the political authority controls the interaction of units in the internal environment, i.e. the ability to ensure the continuity of the situation, whether by imposing respect for the rules of political action by various actors or by imposing penalties in case of breaching these rules. However, this may be a justification for the emergence of the police state that he knows. Harold Laswell "as controlled by specialists in violence or heads of security services".
2. It is represented in the process in which the demands of the various environments, whether individuals or groups, are transferred to alternatives or decisions that are assumed to be compatible with the needs of the majority (ie, general satisfaction), as well as the ability to control the various reactions, and then security at the national level means how to deal with Political power with the various influences that affect it from the external environment such as direct military threats, electronic terrorism, illegal immigration, pollution, organized crime.....

The second topic: Cyber terrorism as one of the threats to the security of countries

The first requirement: Electronic terrorism (concept - causes - characteristics - goals – means)

First: the definition of electronic terrorism

The term electronic terrorism is relatively recent, as it dates back to the beginning of the nineties of the twentieth century as a result of the significant increase in the rates of Internet use and reliance on it in the management of state affairs, which led to the fear that terrorists would use this modern technology with damages that may sometimes exceed those Resulting from traditional terrorist operations, these fears of electronic terrorism increase from opportunities for terrorist organizations to carry out attacks that result in serious damage

Dorothy Denning defines electronic terrorism as “the attack based on attacking a computer, and the threat of it aims to intimidate or compel governments or societies to achieve political, religious or ideological goals, and the attack should be destructive and disruptive to generate fear so that it is similar to the physical acts of terrorism” Electronic terrorism is also defined as “aggression, intimidation, or threat, materially or morally, by using electronic means issued by states, groups or individuals through cyberspace, or to be the target of such aggression in a way that affects the peaceful use of it” (, also known as “activity” Or a deliberate attack with political motives with the aim of influencing government decisions or public opinion by using cyberspace as an aid and mediating factor in carrying out the terrorist act or war through direct attacks by military force on the capabilities of the information infrastructure or through what is considered a moral and psychological influence and through incitement to broadcast Religious hatred and war of ideas, or it takes place in digital form through

the use of new electronic weapons mechanisms in battles taking place in cyberspace, which are limited to the effect of It can be seen on its digital dimension or to infringe on physical targets related to vital infrastructure”, and it is required that the attack be described as electronic terrorism that results in damage to property or individuals and creates a state of fear for the target, and then attacks targeting services are not to a large degree. It is important outside the framework of the concept of electronic terrorism, as the target must be vital and important for the lives of citizens and the work of the state, in addition to that, the attacks of electronic terrorism must be premeditated and planned in the past and aim to destroy the target or cause a high degree of damage, not just causing disruption to the. In his work, electronic terrorism differs from piracy in that piracy means attacking websites and trying to control information, which is far from the concept of electronic terrorism, which means that it is a specific act aimed at intimidating large numbers of citizens.

Second: The causes of electronic terrorism

There is no doubt that electronic terrorism has a number of motives and causes that differ and vary in the degree of importance, and in the extent of the impact, depending on the circumstances that help in its occurrence and achieving its goals.

The tyranny of the political system and the lack of popular participation.

Depriving political forces of freedom of action.

The state's adoption of coercive methods in dealing with citizens.

Absence of national dialogue on basic and crucial issues.

The failure or inability of governments to meet the basic needs of citizens, such as housing and work. unemployment problem.

The dependence of the political system on the outside.

Civilizational crisis and electronic crisis.

As for the special reasons related to the virtual world, which would make electronic terrorism one of the biggest challenges of the current era, as it is an easy destination and an appropriate weapon, and among these reasons:()

1. The weakness of the software and physical infrastructure of the information network and its vulnerability to penetration: the information network was originally designed openly without security restrictions, with a desire to expand and facilitate the entry of users, and because it and its electronic systems contain information gaps that enabled terrorist organizations to exploit these gaps to infiltrate information infrastructures, and the practice of its terrorist sabotage operations, as the organizational and legal vacuum and the absence of control and oversight over the information network that the regulations and laws of some global societies suffer from about electronic terrorism and information crimes is considered one of the main reasons for its spread, and due to the absence of universal and integrated criminal laws and regulations that made criminals deliberately set off. From countries that lack these laws and regulations, and they focus their attacks on countries that have these strict laws in dealing with such cases, which led to the emergence of the problem of conflict of laws.
2. Absence of geographical borders and low level of risk: The absence of specific spatial boundaries in the geographical nature on the Internet, in addition to the lack of clarity of the virtual or digital identity of the user endemic in his open environment, is an opportunity for terrorists so that the computer professional can present himself with the identity and capacity he desires, or That he hides behind a fictitious virtual character, which made it easy for him to launch his terrorist attack electronically without the need for adventure and direct risk, and away from the eyes of censorship and security.
3. Ease of use and low cost: The Internet is of low cost and is characterized by the profitability of both time and effort, which creates opportunities for terrorists to achieve their illegal targets, without the need for huge sources of funding.

Third: The characteristics of electronic terrorism

Electronic terrorism is characterized by a number of characteristics and features that differ from the rest of the crimes, and prevent it from being mixed with ordinary terrorism, and it is possible to summarize the most important of these characteristics and features as follows

- Cyber terrorism is characterized as a transnational terrorist crime that crosses countries and continents, as it is not subject to a limited regional scope.
- The difficulty of discovering crimes of electronic terrorism, due to the lack of experience of some security and judicial agencies in dealing with this type of crime.
- Electronic terrorism does not require violence and force to be perpetrated, but rather requires the presence of a computer connected to the international information network and equipped with some necessary programs.
- The difficulty of proof in electronic terrorism, due to the rapid absence of digital evidence, and the ease of its destruction and destruction.
- Electronic terrorism is characterized by the cooperation of more than one person in committing it.

- The perpetrator of electronic terrorism is usually one of the specialists in the field of information technology, or at least has the ability to know and experience in dealing with the computer and the information network
- Electronic terrorism does not require the presence of the attacker and the target in the same place, as electronic attacks can be carried out from a distance, which facilitates the possibility of attracting new members to terrorist organizations without the need to conduct physical or psychological training for them, meaning that cyberspace provides a new arena for recruitment for terrorist groups. , Electronic terrorist attacks can create damage to a greater number of individuals compared to traditional attacks, which helps terrorist groups to attract more media and governmental attention in a way that helps them achieve their goals more effectively and some believe that attacks in cyberspace will not result in The same destructive effects as those of traditional large-scale attacks that terrorize societies.

Fourth: Electronic means of terrorism

1. E-mail: A service that allows the exchange of messages and information with others through an information network. This service is one of the most prominent services provided by the Internet, because of the speed in delivering the message and the ease of access to it anywhere. The sent electronic message is not linked to a specific place, but rather It can be viewed and read anywhere in the world, and although e-mail has become the most widely used means in various sectors, especially the business sector because it is more easy, secure and quick to deliver messages, it is one of the greatest means used in electronic terrorism, through the use of e-mail in Communication between terrorists and the exchange of information between them. Indeed, in many of the terrorist operations that have occurred recently, e-mail has been one of the means of information and its transmission between those who carry out terrorist operations and those who have sinned against it.
2. Websites: It made it easier for terrorist organizations to expand their activities to extremes through the exchange of opinions, ideas and information, as it is possible for several people to meet in multiple places at one time. It also helped them gather the largest number of followers and supporters by spreading their ideas and principles through these Sites and discussion forums. Indeed, some terrorist organizations create more than one site to ensure wide spread, and even if access to some of these sites is prevented or destroyed, other sites remain accessible.
3. Creation and dissemination of viruses: Viruses are characterized by rapid spread on the Internet, and viruses are one of the most dangerous pests of the information network because of the damage they cause to the information and data system and to changes in the programs or environment in which it works, as well as the ability to multiply, spread and sabotage stored files, and may reach up to Destroying a full operating system, for example, the Melissa virus, which was spread in 1999 by e-mail, and this virus infected the email systems of the US Department of Defense and NATO and caused their failure, which later announced its ability to stop the work of NATO's strategic weapons
4. Electronic espionage: It means the ability to enter illegally and gain access to opponent's networks, without this being accompanied by destruction or sabotage of data and information, such as: information and economic espionage issues, and threatening many elements of national security by spreading rumors and false news to cause confusion Among the members of society electronic espionage aims to obtain information, which may include defensive or offensive military plans, military or peaceful secret plans, or strategic studies or research, and from this process it is possible to prepare maps for computer networks and use them in the future to carry out terrorist operations in the cyberspace
5. Destruction of information systems: Through this form of electronic terrorism, terrorists launch attacks and penetrate the information systems of governmental and non-governmental institutions, international companies or individuals, with the aim of destroying or sabotaging the point of contact and erasing and destroying all assets, data and information on the network and databases. This represents a threat to the integrity of the content and this type of electronic terrorism takes three forms, destroying the site, defacing the site, and blocking the site

Fifth: The objectives of electronic terrorism

Electronic terrorism aims to achieve a number of illegal goals, and we can clarify the most prominent of those goals in light of the following points:

1. Spreading fear and terror among different people, countries and peoples.
2. Disturbing public order and information security and destabilizing peace.
3. Endangering the safety and security of society.
4. Damage and destruction of the information infrastructure by means of communications and information technology, or public and private funds and facilities.
5. Threatening and blackmailing public authorities and international organizations.
6. Revenge of opponents.
7. Advertising, attracting attention and arousing public opinion.

8. Collecting and seizing funds, by hacking some bank and personal accounts, and transferring funds to terrorist groups.

The second requirement: Electronic terrorism as a challenge to the national security of countries

Electronic terrorism is a threat to the national security and stability of many countries as a result of countries using advanced technology in infrastructure and the development of official and unofficial institutions and making them electronic. Possible sympathizers with them (), as the Internet has emerged with its many advantages that cross geographical, cultural, political and even religious borders, and on Internet forums, and through its reality and applications, has the concept of national sovereignty become questionable? Through this method, it became possible to organize meetings between criminal groups to coordinate positions and exchange information and services, as it became possible with the Internet, the increase in cases of penetration of national security

Electronic terrorism depends on the ability to penetrate the Internet to achieve aggressive goals of a mostly political nature, even if it creates humanitarian effects behind it that affect many aspects of life, such as attacking the national flight control systems to cause a collision between trains and attacking the national control systems on railway trains to cause a collision between trains Disrupting banks and financial transformation operations, which harms foreign investment and confidence in investment in general, and harms the national economy, and terrorist organizations may threaten the national security of the state from a political and security point of view by damaging command and control systems and communications or cutting communication networks between Central units and leaders, or disrupting air defense systems or derailing missiles, which threatens the security of countries, and prominent political figures in society threaten to kill or explode national facilities or spread viruses in order to cause damage to information networks and electronic systems, in addition to penetrating e-mail. For heads of state and senior political figures to learn their secrets and access their information and Their data, spying on them, knowing their correspondence and communications, and using them in their terrorist operations, or threatening them to compel them to do certain acts they plan to commit.

Terrorist groups target the national security of the country militarily through electronic terrorism by targeting military sites or infiltrating the security systems in a country, decoding secret codes to control the operation of strategic missile launchers and lethal weapons, disrupting military command and control centers and means of communication for armies with the aim of isolating them from their forces, and gaining access This type of threat is rare for several reasons, the first of which is that it requires deep knowledge of the nature of the target and the nature of the information that must be accessed, a knowledge that only governments possess, in addition to the fact that governments usually isolate Sensitive military information about the world, and does not connect the devices it carries to the outside world in any way, but this does not prevent the danger of terrorist groups inside the country from accessing this information, especially if those groups possess high technical knowledge in penetrating computers

As for the economic threat, reliance on computers has become almost absolute in the world of finance and business, which made these networks, due to their interconnected nature, and their openness to science, an attractive target for terrorists. The validity of this information or its sabotage in a simple way can lead to devastating results and weaken confidence in the economic system. Therefore, attacks against economic information systems can be very harmful, and electronic terrorism threatens economically by breaking into the sites of an international stock exchange or even Infiltrating the communications programs at an international airport and disrupting its flights and causing great confusion for travelers and navigators. For example, a hacker managed to control the computer system in a small American airport and turn off the lights and landing strips for planes. Ministries, government agencies and financial institutions were attacked by a group called the "Red Brigades". By destroying its information centers.

Conclusion

Since God created man on this earth and he has material or moral needs, and one of the most important of these needs after food is to obtain security, and after the individual shifted from living alone to living collectively, the need shifted from individual security to collective security, and as a result of this transformation, various types appeared New security, including military security, economic security and cultural security, and this falls within the so-called national security, and the state may be exposed to many threats, whether internal or external, and the most important of these threats in the modern time (electronic terrorism), as due to the great development that took place in The field of technology and the information revolution, the world has become a small village, and with the huge amount of positives of this development, it has led to the emergence of many negatives, and the most prominent of these negatives is the emergence of the so-called electronic terrorism or digital terrorism, and despite the fact that electronic terrorism is one of the modern crimes Relatively speaking, however, it has become one of the most threats to the security of states, as it targets the infrastructure, database and strategic information of the state security, politically, militarily and economically..., and the availability of advanced equipment and Ease of access to information, and the dependence of most countries at the present time on information technology to manage the political, economic and even military affairs of the state, and this made it

easy for some terrorist groups, especially those with experience in the technological field, to penetrate those institutions and threaten state security.

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Author Information

Omar Saad Khalid

Mansour University College, Iraq

Dr. Warqaa Muhammad Rahim

Center for Strategic and International Studies,
University of Baghdad, Iraq
